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<https://doi.org/10.61796/ejlhss.v1i7.716>**FORM AND FACTORS CAUSING THE MORAL
DECADENCY OF THE MILLENNIAL GENERATION IN
SOCIAL LIFE OF COMMUNITIES****Nur Fazillah**STAI Tgk Chik Pante Kulu Banda Aceh, Indonesia
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Abstract: Moral decadence in the current millennial era occurs when the flow of modernization is able to provide everything that has an impact on the moral decline of the Indonesian population, especially among the youth. The problem of the moral crisis experienced especially among the youth has spread, and can threaten the future of the nation. Planting characters in the family environment is not enough in moral construction because when they grow up the child will find a new environment that will also shape his personality. Planting character in the family environment will become the foundation for further character, but not a few experience decline due to the influence of this new environment. In constructing the morals of the nation's generation, three elements of the state which include society, government and the private sector must build synergy in creating Indonesia's golden generation. As for the government, with its duties and functions as policy makers, it can create educational regulations that are oriented towards instilling noble values, as well as building the character of young Indonesian intellectuals. Character building in formal education institutions has not achieved the expected output. Much of this character education is in the form of theory, without any room for the implementation of character or moral values. Furthermore, the presence of Human Rights (HAM) also becomes a pathology in character building, because Human Rights indirectly limit the domination of educators over students

Keywords: Form, Factors, Moral Decadence, Millennial Generation

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Introduction

The problems that occur in Indonesia are closely related to the level of morality in society, the world of education, especially in elementary schools, is one of the contributors to these problems, ranging from theft, bullying, obscenity, even to acts of violence that result in death. This is a symptom of the moral decadence that occurs in Indonesia's younger generation. There are ten indications of symptoms of moral decadence in students who need to get attention and action from various parties so that changes occur for the better. In order to overcome these problems character education is one way or means to improve morale. As for the Laws and Ministerial Regulations as well as Presidential Instructions (Inpres) it also discusses character education that must be taught and exemplified. In carrying out character education, a guide or principle is needed so that character education can run

effectively. In addition, it is also necessary to pay attention to the methods and models used in teaching character education (Cahyo, 2017: 16).

Decadence is decline or decline. Meanwhile, moral decadence is a setback or decline that is focused on behavior or behavior, personality, and traits. In other terms, that moral decadence is a form of decline or setback of a person's personality, attitude, ethics and morals. Many cultures, lifestyles that are no longer ethical, tend to move freely, contrary to people's lives in Indonesia. Therefore, culture and lifestyle have a negative impact on the character of Indonesian society. In addition, Indonesians tend to quickly imitate foreign cultures because they see them as interesting cultures and consider their culture to be outdated and unattractive, but on the other hand it is also accompanied by moral decadence or what is commonly called Moral Decadence. Moral decadence does not only affect adults but also the younger generation who will continue the nation (Casika et al ., 2023: 13).

With character education the next generation will have a strong character to face the rigors of the times. With character education, it is hoped that the next generation will grow up as a generation that is resilient by sticking to religious teachings. The decadence or moral decline of the younger generation today is caused by the development of globalization which continues to grow rapidly so that over time the morals carried by the younger generation today will also disappear and threaten the future of the nation. To face the current era of technological advancement, the Millennial generation must have high competitiveness. Although it is emphasized that the millennial generation has high competitiveness, ethics and morals are also not ruled out. The main reason underlying the statement above is because the main reason for character education in Islam aims to balance material and spiritual needs (Casika et al ., 2023: 13).

The damage to the nation's morals can be observed from the fading behavior of students who are observed from the way they behave, speak words that are impolite and unethical. This study aims to describe the handling of moral decadence through the application of peace-loving and nationalism character education. In reducing the moral decline of students at elementary school age , the school instills a character education of peace-loving and nationalism through habituation, integration in learning, and through school culture. In implementing character education, it is not only the efforts of the school, but also the need for collaboration between all elements, starting from the elements of education, family, and the community environment. These are steps to reduce or even prevent morally degenerate behaviors that occur at elementary school age (Erviana, 2021: 1).

kepo " generation , before deciding to purchase a product, they first seek information via the internet and social media. Reviews about products on the internet and social media are their referrals. The term word of mouth will change to the word of the internet or the word of social media. The research results of the Alvara Research Center in 2015 found that the product information most millennials are looking for on the internet is information about prices, product features, followed by promotion programs and customer reviews . The explosion in consumption of gadgets and the internet by the millennial generation directly or indirectly has an impact on selling channel sales. The phenomenon of the proliferation of online stores is one of the indications. Apart from online shops, forums, social media are now widely used as selling channels. The skyrocketing number of internet usage makes 2020 certainly an indication of the increasingly exciting development of online channel channels (Budi, 2020)

The millennial generation is a social society that is literate and adaptable to technology. They tend to like to use technology to facilitate all activities, including shopping activities. Advances in payment technology have made this generation even more cashless (tend not to carry cash). The convenience of paying for shopping via debit cards, e-money credit cards, internet banking and others

is easily adopted by urban middle-class millennials. So that the existence of urban middle-class millennials will certainly be a trigger for the development of cashless payments. In the future, traditional payment instruments will shift to modern payment instruments (Budi, 2020).

Communication behavior of the millennial generation and generation Z in the digital era in Kuranji District from ten informants. Four behaviors of the millennial generation and generation Z were formed, namely communication behavior from active to passive caused by gadgets, reduced face-to-face communication caused by gadgets, not focusing on communication caused by gadgets, and online communication behavior caused by gadgets. In this study, it can be concluded that the behavior of the millennial generation and generation Z, which was originally interactive before using the device, after using the device the communication process becomes passive, so that effective communication does not occur (Zis et al., 2021: 69).

Islam is *Manhajul Hayah* (system of life) that guides humans towards the path of salvation. There are no orders contained in Islamic teachings unless there are benefits. On the other hand, there is no prohibition stated in this unless there is an obstacle that blocks it. That is why Islam completely rejects the ignorance of modern ignorance. Men and women are brought together not for entertainment and to have fun without purpose. The universal goal of the meeting of these two different types of creatures is to give birth to a noble and pious society.

The teachings of Islam have three main foundations, namely creed, shari'ah and morals. *Aqidah* is related to faith, belief. Shari'ah concerns the rules that must be implemented by humans in order to serve God. While morality is the behavior displayed by a person in his daily life related to his relationship with Allah, humans or other creatures. The three main foundations are related to one another so that they become one unit. *Aqidah* means little if someone does not practice shari'ah, and vice versa and also shari'ah means nothing if he has no morals. *Aqidah* is also closely related to morals (Baulay & Pasa, 2012: 53).

The link or relationship of the three Islamic foundations above is that religion in this case acts as a countermeasure for all forms of moral decadence experienced by adolescents. Therefore, religious thoughts that are taken from the right source will not be mixed up and will not be penetrated by other elements in it. With its originality, it rejects foreign elements that are aggressive because it has its own stronghold, namely Divine protection. Thus, it will not be dangerous for adolescents with the presence of unfavorable foreign elements if they have been equipped with a large number of true Islamic civilizations and have received adequate religious education and have their intellectual equipment straightened out with guidance and the basics of true religion, so that they will not accept except religious ideas and teachings that show a bright and bright path (Ahmad, 2008: 52).

Then, religion also plays a role in tackling drug abuse and the like among young people or adolescents which is realized in the form of religious education through religious activities. Education administrators hold activities with religious themes or revive the spirit of spirituality in the school environment and youth association, so that in this community a vision and culture can be formed that is pivotal to respecting the sustainability of life rather than a race (hunt) to an early death. They need to be involved in activities with the pattern of "diversion " or activities with a pattern of resistance (critical movements and praxis) against all forms of misleading and destructive culture. Adolescents whose personality is formed into a force of resistance will easily offset and defeat the charged influences defeating them (Muchsini & Abdul, 2009: 139).

Methods

This research was conducted using library research (library research) . If the researcher does not have his own reading sources, then he can look at the library, both formal institutional libraries and private libraries. This library research is also research conducted in the library or elsewhere as long as there are relevant reading sources. Good reading sources must meet three criteria, namely relevance, completeness, and up-to-date (except for historical research, this research actually uses old reading sources). Relevance is related to the suitability between the variables studied and the theory put forward, completeness is related to the number of sources read, and sophistication is related to the time dimension. The newer the source used, the more up-to-date the theory will be (Sugiyono, 2013: 66).

Results and Discussion

- **Forms of Moral Decadence**

- Some forms of deviated moral decadence include , namely:

- **Free association and Free Sex**

- Free association and free sex is one of the characteristics of western culture, the culture of people who do not believe and have no civilization. In a country where there are no social boundaries between men and women, social relations are not controlled by religious norms, so these associations will have very fatal consequences. In 1955's Kinsey has published a book on the results of research on sexual behavior of the human female (sexual behavior of women). In the book it is told that 50% of women since they were in school have known sexual life outside of marriage. 64% of women who are married and work in an office have had sexual intercourse before marriage. As a striking consequence is that many children are born without knowing who the father is, and it is not something strange or taboo for men to marry women who are pregnant (Muchsin, 2009: 140).

- **Crime or Acts of Violence**

- Looking at juvenile delinquency both in cities and in villages, it will be obvious that the values of religious teachings have been neglected. This is one form of moral decline among adolescents. In several cities, it is common for junior or senior high school students to be hostile towards each other individually or in groups, and even fights often occur between groups and between schools. Other symptoms can be found, teenagers commit acts of violence such as persecution and murder. In essence, these actions violate commendable values (mahmudah). Persecution which is a threat to health and certain limbs that is carried out by teenagers is generally preceded by small fights. Sometimes these fights develop into more serious and more complex negative effects. Fights often occur between school children and fellow school children, between organized youth groups and other youth groups.

- **Lifestyle Changes**

- In today's era, many young women wear half-naked clothes and excessive make-up. Which in fact is very contrary to Islamic teachings. The way of dress and style of dress of the youth is one of many moral decadence whose behavior has a stimulating effect on lust. This carefree lifestyle is considered a fun and fulfilling lifestyle. So that this lifestyle has taken

root in their lives.

- **Distributing and Consuming Narcotics**

- When teenagers experience situations that are difficult to control and even frustrating, not a few of them solve it through the wrong path, namely by consuming illegal drugs and even drugs. According to most teenagers, this method is the only way to resolve their anxiety. In fact, due to bad association and lack of understanding of religion, they become dealers and consumers of illegal drugs.
- There was a reaction from various groups, both in the government and the community, the war campaign against drugs began to bloom. This is proven both by the existence of training and counseling activities as well as by making banners on the streets that read about activities to fight drugs. This is done so that if drugs are not fought, then it will become the consumption of the youth of the nation's hope. If this happens to the young generation of our beloved country, then this country will lose the generation that is expected to be the nation's successor in the future.

- **Factors Causing Moral Decadence**

- Several factors of moral decadence are in among others , namely:

- **Family environment**

- In fact, the influence of the family environment is very large on adolescents. However, this influence is not limited to when he is a teenager, but has started since he was a baby, even since he was in the womb. Perhaps it can be said that the influence he received as a child was far greater and more decisive in his later life. Because of his childhood experiences, it helped shape his personality: what he saw, heard, and felt in his childhood life. Does he often witness or hear things that are not compatible in his family, for example the incompatibility of his parents, there is often tension and misunderstandings between one another in the family, then the newly growing child will experience a turbulent soul, because he often feels anxious and afraid.
- Even further, it can be said that his belief in God or his various beliefs will be greatly influenced by the atmosphere of family relationships at that time. Families who live far from religion, it is impossible to provide religious guidance for their children. In religious development, the parental factor is actually very decisive, because the sense of religion will be intertwined in the child's personality at the same time as when he was small. If the religion is only obtained later through superficial teaching, then the religion will be known, but it will not penetrate deep into his soul. And even more dangerous, if children have entered their teenage years, which are full of problems and turmoil, still do not know religion, then all the difficulties and emotional pressures that they experience, they cannot overcome or reduce on their own, because they are not able to pray and ask God for help. This is where teenagers start running in various ways that sometimes ignore moral values (Daradjat, 1975: 19-21).

- **Close Friend or Friend**

- Close friends can influence one's beliefs and thoughts. Therefore friendship relations have a very important influence in the formation of attitudes and personality of adolescents. However, not many parents and teachers are aware of it. They only realized when it was too late. Because of the strong influence of friendship ties, parents and teachers can find out the beliefs and personality of a teenager from their close friends (Basya, 2009: 284).

- **Foreign Culture**

- Teenagers are a group of people who are most susceptible to outside influences, because they easily experience emotional turmoil due to the changes and growth they go through. In foreign cultural relations, it is teenagers who are more affected, when compared to adults and children. There are positive and negative influences of foreign culture. However, when viewed among adolescents the negative influence is far more dominating. Where, it is the negative influence that causes moral decadence in adolescents. The negative influence of foreign culture on Indonesian youth is actually not that big, if you remember that Indonesia is a developing country moving towards progress.

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- **Community Environment**

- If in society there is no longer visible moral superiority, where manners are not maintained, religion and certain values are no longer visible, and fraud, strife and violation of the rights of others become commonplace, then the adolescent's soul will be increasingly depressed. and rebelled. If these adolescents who are full of idealism, have not received religious education since they were young, or in their personality are very lacking in religious elements, then the pressure of feelings or frustration related to that will be easily expressed in the form of attacks and violence, because the controllers that arise from within is very lacking. So their target might extend to opposing religion, maybe even not believing in God anymore (Daradjat, 1975: 23)

- **Educational institutions**

- The educational institution in question is the school. A good school should provide a lot of moral and religious education. So that it will create a generation of youth who are good in morals as well as intellect. However, in this day and age. Many of the existing schools do not provide this education to their students, only their academic grades are prioritized. So, government agencies need to implement a curriculum that prioritizes morals or children's morals and religious education. In Indonesia, the latest curriculum has been implemented, the core of which is religion, social, intelligence and psychomotor.

Conclusion

Moral decadence in the current millennial era occurs when the flow of modernization is able to provide everything that has an impact on the moral decline of the Indonesian population, especially among the youth. This of course must be resolved immediately, bearing in mind the ideals of an

advanced Indonesia which have always been echoed, but so far have not been in accordance with what has been presented. Building the morals of the younger generation in the millennial era is certainly not an easy matter, and must be done from an early age. In the writer's opinion, there are two factors that are the cause of the moral decline in the current millennial era, namely the family environment, and the influence of the environment and the mass media. The family environment becomes the first school for a child, in where the character will be determined by the family environment. Furthermore, the influence of the environment and the mass media will also shape the true identity. It is at this stage that determines whether a person has good morals or not. Today, the influence of the environment and the mass media or technological developments have caused moral decadence because they misinterpret and take advantage of technological developments

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